

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D1.4

Portfolio of Project Promotional Material

Planned delivery date: 31st May 2023 (M12)

Actual submission date:

Deliverable leader: Partner 2 – ERINN Innovation

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Type of deliverable: Report

Work package Leader: Partner 1 – IFREMER

Version: 1.0

Project funded by the European Commission within the HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01	
Dissemination Level	
PU Public	X
PP Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO Confidential, only for member of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

GA No. 101056957 - PREP4BLUE

Start date of the project: June 1st, 2022

www.Prepare4Blue.eu

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Summary

This report provides an overview of the **PREP4BLUE** Portfolio of Project Promotional Material (Deliverable 1.4). The purpose of Deliverable 1.4 is to facilitate widespread communication and dissemination of PREP4BLUE results to a range of stakeholders including those in policy, industry, academia and the general public over the course of the project. The report describes the communications tools available at M12 (May 2023).

The portfolio of dissemination tools and resources contains: the project branding, logo and style guidelines, promotional factsheets, project website, poster, PowerPoint template, virtual backgrounds, pull-up banner and social media presence.

PREP4BLUE communications activities will run for the duration of the project, with additional supports for partners in their communication and dissemination activities. All tools and resources will be maintained throughout the project and some aspects of the portfolio will be maintained after the project's end (e.g., the public PREP4BLUE website).

1. Introduction

The **PREP4BLUE** Portfolio of Project Promotional Material has been developed to enable effective and efficient communication of the project's activities and results to a diverse range of stakeholders including European citizens, researchers, businesses, industry and policy makers.

The role of the portfolio is to support partners as they promote **PREP4BLUE**, raise awareness of its findings, disseminate research results, and engage with the public throughout the duration of the project. The portfolio contains all communications resources developed as of May 2023 (M12) and will be maintained and updated as the project progresses. Additional resources may be added to the portfolio as needed by T1.5 leaders ERINN Innovation (ERINN).

The first step in developing the portfolio was to create a strong brand for the project, represented primarily by the project logo. In line with the conceived brand, ERINN has developed a toolkit of dissemination resources which includes:

- Brand guidelines
- Logo

- Factsheets
- Public website
- Poster
- PowerPoint template
- Virtual backgrounds
- Pull up banners
- Social media presence

The **PREP4BLUE** Portfolio of Project Promotional Material is available to download from the **PREP4BLUE** Teams or can be requested from Task 1.5 leader ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu).

2. Results

This section provides an overview of the materials contained within the **PREP4BLUE** Portfolio of Project Promotional Material. The **PREP4BLUE** Brand Guidelines can be viewed in full in Annex 1.

2.1. Project Logo

The project logo is a key element of the **PREP4BLUE** brand that is included on all project promotional material. The **PREP4BLUE** logo is constructed using upper-case bold lettering and a specially hand-crafted accompanying icon. The logo is designed to mirror and complement the branding developed for Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030' (the Mission).

PREP4BLUE logo in full colour and in single colour

2.2. Factsheet

A project factsheet was designed to give a general audience an overview of the **PREP4BLUE** project. The factsheet provides an introduction to the Mission, outlines the justification for the project, its objectives and expected results and impacts. Also provided is a map showing the location of project partner sites and the four Lighthouse sites. The factsheet format is a double-sided full colour A4 leaflet, chosen for ease of use by all partners. Both web and print versions are available on the **PREP4BLUE** Teams site or can be requested from Task 1.5 lead ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu).

PREP4BLUE factsheet in English

PREP4BLUE
METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

www.prep4blue.eu
@PREP4BLUE

www.missionoceanwaters.eu
@euissionocean

The Mission
As a strategic way to find innovative solutions to some of Europe's greatest challenges, the **five EU Missions** aim to deliver concrete results by 2030, contributing to European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals. **Mission: Restore our Ocean & Waters** seeks to restore the health of our oceans and waters by protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, preventing and eliminating pollution, and making the Blue Economy sustainable, carbon neutral and circular. These goals will be achieved through key demonstrator sites or 'lighthouses' which will act as Research and Innovation (RI) hubs that will develop, demonstrate and deploy new solutions to support their wider implementation and realisation across Europe.

Project Objective
PREP4BLUE's objective is to facilitate the successful implementation of **Mission: Restore our Ocean & Waters**, particularly during its first phase (2022-2025). Through a series of pilots at the Mission's demonstrator or 'lighthouse' sites, PREP4BLUE will develop tools and services that will assist with the co-design and co-implementation of RI solutions with European citizens and Mission stakeholders. The development of a knowledge ecosystem and innovative communication activities will ensure cohesion and connectivity across sectors, and engage citizens and stakeholders with the Mission.

At a Glance
Programme: HORIZON MISS 2021-OCEAN 01
Type of Action: Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
Duration: June 2022 – May 2025
Coordinator: Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer, France
Budget: €4,997,690

Expected Results

- A dedicated structure to ensure alignment and connectivity between EC, international, national and regional initiatives contributing to Mission objectives.
- Tested and validated methodologies to ensure active engagement and participation of European citizens and stakeholders in the co-design and co-implementation of the Mission's R&I activities.
- Best practice knowledge management system supported by AI digital tools, to ensure that innovative solutions are identified, managed and effectively taken up by Mission stakeholders.
- Database of relevant projects and their innovative solutions with high potential to contribute to the achievement of the Mission objectives in each of the Lighthouse sites.
- Recommendations for the creation of an enabling environment from a regulatory and economic perspective, that paves the way for public and private investment in future initiatives aligned with the Mission objectives.
- Inspiring and creative communication strategy and actions to encourage citizens and stakeholders to engage with the Mission objectives.

Project Network
The three-year PREP4BLUE project brings together 17 organisations from research, industry, government and non-profit sectors in eight European countries, working across four Lighthouse sites in the Atlantic-Arctic Sea Basin, the Baltic and North Seas, the Danube River Basin and the Mediterranean Sea.

1. Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer (France)
2. ERINN Innovation (Ireland)
3. Joint Programming Initiative for Healthy and Productive Seas and Oceans (Belgium)
4. KIM German Marine Research Consortium (Germany)
5. Flanders Marine Institute (Belgium)
6. ST. De Bruine Cluster (Belgium)
7. Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft (Germany)
8. Confédération de Régions Maritimes (France)
9. University of Southern Denmark (Denmark)
10. Centro Tecnológico Dal Mar - Fundación (Spain)
11. Njordland Research Institute (Norway)
12. Institut de Ciències del Mar (Spain)
13. MARIS STI Centre for Energy, Climate and Marine, University College Cork (Ireland)
14. EuroMarine Association (France)
15. National Research Council of Italy (Italy)
16. Sustainable Projects (Germany)
17. Galway Atlantic Aquaria (Ireland)

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www.prep4blue.eu
@PREP4BLUE
www.missionoceanwaters.eu
@euissionocean

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Designed and developed by ERINN Innovation

2.3. Public website

The project website (<https://prep4blue.eu/>) is the main tool for promoting **PREP4BLUE**, sharing updates, accessing outputs and results, and disseminating the project’s vision, work packages and results to a wide audience.

The **landing page** of the website contains information about the project and calls to action to discover more about project workflow, results and resources, news and events.

The **About** section includes the project overview, information about project partners, a breakdown of the work packages and an introduction the Mission. The information on project partners includes an interactive map that shows the location of each partner site.

PREP4BLUE landing page and Project Overview

The **News** and **Events** sections are used to promote both **PREP4BLUE** and Mission specific activities. Items can be filtered by category, so that users can tailor content to their area of interest.

PREP4BLUE regularly publishes news articles on the project website featuring activities that partners have organised or are involved in. Articles have been published about **PREP4BLUE** activities such as the project kick-off meeting, launch of the survey on citizen engagement and the launch of knowledge transfer activities within **PREP4BLUE** for example. To support the Mission, articles have been published on the Mission Charter and an illustrative, case study style article has been shared about project partner JPI Oceans' pledges to the Mission Charter.

Upcoming events are frequently added to the Events page. Both **PREP4BLUE** and **Mission** specific events are shared and posts are regularly updated as new information becomes available.

News and Events pages showing featured news and filter

The **Results** section will be used to house key project outputs such as public deliverables, publications and reports. They will be added to the page later in the project once they become available for public viewing.

The **Resources** section contains a combination of both project and Mission specific resources. It contains **PREP4BLUE** resources such as the project factsheet and press release. It also contains resources developed by the Commission to promote and raise awareness of the Mission.

Resources page showing resources and filters

Additional pages can and will be added to the website as needed. Since being launched a dedicated page on the Mission Charter has been added to the website. It is planned that a helpdesk for project stakeholders will also be added to the website in time. Additional pages can be added to the main menu bar or can be added as sub-pages selected from a drop-down list under main menu pages.

Mission Charter page with introduction to the charter and resources

2.4. Poster

A poster has been designed to allow partners to present the **PREP4BLUE** project at conferences and events. It contains an introduction to the Mission, project objectives, project overview and contact details.

PREP4BLUE poster template

prep4blue.eu
@PREP4BLUE
missionoceanwaters.eu
@eumissionocean

The Mission

As a visionary way to find innovative solutions to some of Europe's greatest challenges, the five EU Missions aim to deliver concrete results by 2030, contributing to European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals. 'Mission: Restore our Ocean & Waters' seeks to restore the health of our oceans and waters by protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, preventing and eliminating pollution, and making the Blue Economy sustainable, carbon neutral and circular.

At a Glance

Programme: HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01
Type of Action: Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
Duration: June 2022 – May 2025
Coordinator: L'Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer, France
Budget: €4,997,690

Project Objective

PREP4BLUE's objective is to facilitate the successful implementation of Mission: Restore our Ocean & Waters, particularly during its first phase (2022-2025). Through pilots at the Missions demonstrator or 'Lighthouse' sites, PREP4BLUE will develop tools and services that will support the co-design and co-implementation of R&I solutions with European citizens and Mission stakeholders. The development of a knowledge ecosystem and innovative communication activities will ensure cohesion and connectivity across sectors, and engage citizens and stakeholders with the Mission.

Designed and developed by erinn innovation

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2.5. Presentation template

A **PREP4BLUE** PowerPoint presentation template has been developed for use at external and internal events when presenting the **PREP4BLUE** project. It is available in standard (4:3) format. The template includes a cover slide with a space for title and presenter names, several different main body slides, and a concluding slide with contact details for the project representatives. The slide template was developed following the brand guidelines and is available in the project colours. The template is available on the **PREP4BLUE** Teams site or can be requested from Task 1.5 leader ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu).

PREP4BLUE presentation slides

2.6. Virtual backgrounds

Different virtual backgrounds were created for partners to use when representing the project on online meeting platforms such as Zoom or Teams. A number of options are provided using the **PREP4BLUE** logo and logo elements.

The Zoom backgrounds can be downloaded from the **PREP4BLUE** Teams or can be requested from T1.5 leader ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu).

PREP4BLUE Virtual Background Options

2.7. Pull up banner

A pull up banner has been designed for use at **PREP4BLUE** events including conferences, consortium meetings and community events. The pull up banner has a tag line and image, and includes the project logo, EU disclaimer, contact information and the **PREP4BLUE** website and social media handles. Also included are the contact details for the project coordinator and manager. The banner's dimensions are 850x2100mm. The pull up banner is available to download from the **PREP4BLUE** Teams or can be requested from Task 1.5 lead ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu).

PREP4BLUE
METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

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missionoceanwaters.eu
[@eumissionocean](https://twitter.com/eumissionocean)

Co-creating the methods and tools required to achieve Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030

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2.8. Social media presence

Social networking is an important element of the **PREP4BLUE** communication and dissemination strategy. A dedicated social media channels has been established for the project and is actively maintained by Task 1.5 leader ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu).

Twitter was selected as the best channel to engage with as wide an audience as possible. The project uses the handle @PREP4BLUE.

Partners are encouraged to develop posts that they would like to be shared on the **PREP4BLUE** Twitter page or to send any content that they would like shared to Task 1.5 leader ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu).

PREP4BLUE Twitter Profile Page

Examples of PREP4BLUE social media posts

3. Conclusions

The purpose of this Deliverable 1.4 was to create a portfolio of dissemination tools and resources to effectively promote the **PREP4BLUE** project and to assist partners as they carry out communication and dissemination activities. This report provided an overview of the portfolio of communication tools that is available as of May 2023 (M12).

The **Portfolio of Project Promotional Material** includes: The portfolio of dissemination tools and resources contains: the project branding, logo and style guidelines, promotional factsheets, project website, poster, PowerPoint template, virtual backgrounds, pull-up banner and social media presence. All these elements have been discussed in this report. Additional resources will be developed as needed over the course of the project. All communication and dissemination tools are available on the **PREP4BLUE** Teams or can be accessed by contacting Task 1.5 leader ERINN (sarah@erinn.eu).

4. Partners involved in the work

Materials for the portfolio were developed by ERINN Innovation. Before being finalised and made live, materials were sent to the project coordinator and other partners where relevant for feedback and approval.

5. Revision table

Version 1	05.05.23, Sarah Sarsfield, ERINN Innovation
Version N+1.+1	DD.MM.YYYY, Author
Version N+2.N+2	DD.MM.YYYY, Author

ANNEX 1 – Brand Guidelines

Brand Guidelines

PREP4BLUE
Brand Guidelines

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3 PREP4BLUE
Brand Guidelines

INTRODUCTION

Brand guidelines

The guidelines set out in this manual offer the means by which all PREP4BLUE partners can achieve the high standards of project presentation in all dissemination activities. It is recommended that partners follow the standards given.

For any queries regarding the implementation of the PREP4BLUE brand guidelines, please contact Cliona Ni Cheallachain (cliona@erinn.eu).

www.prep4blue.eu

4 PREP4BLUE Brand Guidelines

LOGO

This section gives you guidelines on how to use the logo in any format, for example the recommended type face to use, the colour palette and best use of the logo on different backgrounds.

5 PREP4BLUE
Brand Guidelines

COLOUR VERSIONS

The PREP4BLUE logo is constructed using a combination of bold lettering and a specially crafted accompanying icon. The full colour logo should always be used as the main logo.

The one colour version logos are intended for applications that are restricted in colour, such as fax, memo etc. or any time it is not possible to use colour printing techniques.

Full colour logo

White logo

Black logo

6 PREP4BLUE Brand Guidelines

CORRECT USE OF LOGO

Colour background variations

The preferred background for the PREP4BLUE logo is white, but there will be some instances where the logo needs to be used over a colour other than white. In this case, you may have to use either the white or black version of the logo.

Whether the logo is being used in full colour, black or

white, please ensure that the logo is always legible and there is sufficient contrast between all the elements to ensure the text is legible.

Photographic background variations

It may be necessary to use the logo over images. In all cases, it is important to ensure that all elements of the logo are clearly visible.

Correct
The full colour logo is only fully visible on a light background.

Incorrect
The full colour logo is not fully visible on a background similar in colour to the logo.

Correct
The white logo is only fully visible on a dark background.

Incorrect
The black logo is not fully visible on a dark background.

Correct
The black logo is only fully visible on a light background.

Incorrect
The white logo is not fully visible on a light background.

Correct
The full colour logo is fully visible on a light image.

Incorrect
The full colour logo is not fully visible on an image similar in colour to the logo.

Correct
The white logo is fully visible on a dark image.

Incorrect
The black logo is not fully visible on a dark image.

Correct
The black logo is fully visible on a light image.

Incorrect
The white logo is not fully visible on a light image.

7 PREP4BLUE Brand Guidelines

Clearance space

Clearance space is the area surrounding the logo that should be kept free of other graphical elements. You should allow sufficient space around the logo.

The minimum required space to use around the logo is the approximate height and width of any letter in the "PREP4BLUE" logotype.

Clearance space for logo

Minimum size

The PREP4BLUE logo can be increased to any size you require however the minimum size the logo should be displayed at approximately 70 mm in width. Where possible, the logo should not be used below this size as legibility will be compromised.

Minimum size
= 70mm width

8 PREP4BLUE
Brand Guidelines

INCORRECT USE OF LOGO

What not to do

Do not recreate elements of the artwork. Do not modify elements or alter colours. Please adhere to the guidelines below.

Do not distort logo

Do not modify colours

Do not rearrange elements

Do not add elements

Do not distort the icon

Do not modify proportion

9 PREP4BLUE
Brand Guidelines

TYPEFACES

Primary — Myriad Pro (Graphic Design Use)

Myriad Pro is the primary PREP4BLUE typeface. This simple, modern font helps communicate ideas clearly and confidently. It is highly legible in both print and digital communications. It is available in a range of weights: from light to bold.

Myriad Pro is primarily used for print design.

Myriad Pro Light

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 @*?!&%+="

Myriad Pro Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 @*?!&%+="

Secondary – Arial (General Use)

Arial is the secondary PREP4BLUE typeface. **Arial** reflects the clean look of the primary typeface and should be used whenever possible within Microsoft Office applications i.e. Word, Powerpoint, Excel etc.

Arial can be used for all standard communication materials e.g. letters/faxes/reports/emails etc.

Arial is packaged with all Microsoft and Macintosh computers.

Arial Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 @*?!&%+="

Arial Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789 @*?!&%+="

10 PREP4BLUE
Brand Guidelines

COLOUR PALETTE

Print

The CMYK values are required when preparing materials for professional print jobs.

In-office printing will provide varied results depending on equipment and as a result, 100% colour accuracy cannot be expected.

Web

The RGB values are required when preparing materials for the web.

It is important to note that the calibration of monitors, desktop printers and projection equipment can vary. Please adhere to the RGB values provided to ensure consistency across all materials for the web.

<p>Blue</p> <p>C 100 M 80 R 3 Y 0 G 78 K 0 B 162</p>	<p>Turquoise</p> <p>C 76 M 13 R 2 Y 21 G 168 K 0 B 192</p>	<p>Light Blue</p> <p>C 74 M 28 R 45 Y 0 G 150 K 0 B 211</p>
<p>Green</p> <p>C 37 M 0 R 174 Y 100 G 209 K 0 B 54</p>	<p>Dark Blue</p> <p>C 100 M 87 R 32 Y 19 G 64 K 6 B 129</p>	<p>Grey</p> <p>C 71 M 60 R 61 Y 59 G 66 K 4 B 67</p>

11 PREP4BLUE
Brand Guidelines

APPLICATION

12 PREP4BLUE Brand Guidelines

POWERPOINT PRESENTATION

Please follow the PowerPoint template where possible. We suggest using 20pt for the body font size and at least 32pt for headings.

Title slide layout

Content slide layouts

Closing slide layout

13 PREP4BLUE
Brand Guidelines

WORD TEMPLATE

Please follow the Word template for project deliverables and reports. The recommended font is Arial.

14 PREP4BLUE
Brand Guidelines

EU FUNDING

15 PREP4BLUE Brand Guidelines

The EU Missions

To align with the EU Missions branding, along with the matching the typeface and colour palette, various elements that form part of the Missions visual identity have been used throughout the PREP4BLUE templates and resources.

Further information is contained in the EC Mission brand guidelines. Please contact the Work Package 2 Leaders as well as ERINN Innovation for guidance on when to use the Mission templates and resources.

A 'Mission Restore our
Ocean and Waters' initiative.

Different elements from the EU Missions brand guidelines

16 PREP4BLUE Brand Guidelines

Acknowledgement of EU funding

All publications or any other dissemination relating to results should include the EU emblem and the following statement to indicate that said results were generated with the assistance of financial support from the EU:

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A combined EU emblem and disclaimer graphic is available in the PREP4BLUE logo suite.

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EU emblem

High-resolution versions of the emblem can be found here: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en